

Is the ‘Calculator for Words’ analogy useful for
communicating about LLMs?

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Abstract

Large language models (LLMs) are fundamentally different from search engines, functioning more as ‘vibe-machines’ than information retrieval systems. However, conveying appropriate expectations and usage modes for these novel interfaces remains challenging. This paper critically examines Willison’s ‘calculator for words’ analogy and Bucci’s counter-arguments, analysing the strengths and limitations of this metaphor.

While we argue that the ‘calculator for words’ analogy serves as an effective negative heuristic – discouraging users from treating generative AI prompts as search engine queries – it falls short in providing positive intuition for effective LLM utilisation. To address this limitation, we propose a novel conceptual framework: ‘maps of no territory.’

Drawing inspiration from Borges’ ‘On Exactitude in Science,’ our ‘maps of no territory’ analogy aims to provide more nuanced intuitions for general audiences, guiding them towards effective use while steering them away from problematic applications. This metaphor offers a more comprehensive understanding of LLMs’ nature, capabilities, and limitations, potentially fostering more informed and responsible engagement with these powerful AI systems.

Keywords: AI Literacy, Large Language Model, Digital Epistemology, Borges

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047 1 Introduction

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049 One of the most pervasive mistakes I see people using with large language model tools like
050 ChatGPT is trying to use them as a search engine. ... I like to think of language models
051 like ChatGPT as a calculator for words. ... Want them to work with specific facts? Paste
052 those into the language model as part of your original prompt! (Willison, 2023)
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055 In workshops across 2023 and 2024, we have tried to communicate to rooms of
056 bemused academics about the nature and affordances of Large Language Models
057 (LLMs)¹ In these sessions, we have consistently emphasised the limitations of the
058 conversational interface these models present and cautioned against their misuse as
059 search engines. We have found that Willison’s analogy of a ‘Calculator for words’ is a
060 useful lie-to-academics (Pratchett et al, 2000, see) to communicate this state.
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063 This paper aims to critically examine the ‘calculator for words’ analogy, analysing
064 arguments both for and against its use. We will explore this analogy through various
065 conceptual lenses and introduce our proposed alternative analogy. While we contend
066 that the ‘calculator for words’ analogy serves as an excellent negative heuristic – effec-
067 tively teaching audiences what not to do by discouraging the treatment of generative
068 AI prompts as search engine queries – it falls short in providing a positive intuition
069 for effective LLM utilisation.
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072 Our primary challenge lies in developing an analogy that encapsulates the nuanced
073 experience of interacting with LLMs – a process more akin to ‘talking as programming’
074 than to engaging with chatbots or search engines. When discussing Generative AI, an
075 apt analogy is crucial.
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078 These tools fundamentally differ from search engines; they do not retrieve facts
079 but rather manipulate language, expanding and explicating the implicit information
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082 ¹In this paper, we will refer to both Generative AI and LLMs. While most of the time, the two terms are
083 synonymous, we highlight the distinction between the services which provide an interface and additional
084 affordances as a Generative AI, while the specific statistical model providing token inference is the LLM.
085 This is because, the choices the designers make in system prompt and affordances in presentation change
086 how we use and think about the output of the LLM.
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contained within a prompt. In essence, they function as ‘vibe-machines.’ The question then becomes: How can we effectively communicate the capabilities of this alien intelligence, transcending the familiar narratives that have shaped our understanding of AI (Mollick, 2023c)? More succinctly: What analogy can capture the epistemology of an LLM that avoids the extremes of Skynet or Google search?

In response to this challenge, we propose a novel analogy for conceptualising LLMs: ‘maps of no territory.’

Willison’s ‘calculator for words’ analogy attempts to reframe how users approach LLMs, shifting away from the search engine paradigm. By drawing parallels between linguistic manipulation and mathematical computation, this analogy aims to highlight the deterministic and input-dependent nature of LLM interactions. However, as we will explore, this comparison also introduces its own set of conceptual challenges and potential misunderstandings.

In the following sections, we will dissect the ‘calculator for words’ analogy for its strengths and weaknesses. We find that the use of ‘a calculator for words’ is an appropriate negative analogy – ensuring that users pay attention to the inputs they provide. However, we find that it does not maintain salience after more thorough consideration, nor do LLMs provide the reliability of output that calculators provide.

In ‘maps of no territory,’ we borrow the map-territory analogy from *On Exactitude in Science* by Borges and Hurley (1998, 325) in service towards a new analogy for a general audience, providing more effective intuitions for the audience and steering them away from problematic uses.

2 For ‘Calculators for words’

The primary objective of the ‘calculator for words’ analogy is to discourage the use of LLM-powered services as fact-retrieval systems (Willison, 2023). While there are opportunities to engage in ‘Retrieval Augmented Generation,’ where the source text is

139 automatically included in the user’s prompt (Lewis et al, 2020), most services and some
140 users treat the unvarnished output equivalently to search engine results, Wikipedia
141 entries, or human conversation. In addition to this, LLM outputs often adopt a con-
142 fident and professional register, lacking the most common tells of uncertainty or
143 unreliability.
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147 Various analogies have been proposed to communicate the potential unreliability
148 of LLM outputs. Mollick employs the notion of enthusiastic but erratic ‘high-school
149 interns,’ (Mollick, 2023a) while Willison advocates for ‘calculators for words.’ In sepa-
150 rate work, Ballsun-Stanton likens LLMs to a ‘drunk university tutor – always confident
151 and usually correct.’ While none of these analogies capture the full complexity of
152 LLMs, each aims to be persuasive in its own right.
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157 These analogys serve to counter what might be termed, somewhat facetiously,
158 ‘the world’s worst interface.’² When LLM outputs are presented in a chat format or
159 alongside search results, they benefit from a halo effect: the conversational tone and
160 register lend unwarranted credibility to the content, while the proximity to search
161 results evokes the trust users have developed through years of web searching. This
162 presentation can lead to an overestimation of the LLM’s reliability and accuracy.
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167 Among these analogies, ‘calculator for words’ stands out as the least anthropo-
168 morphising. It suggests a mechanistic manipulation of language where inputs are
169 entirely under human control. This framing shifts the perceived locus of control back
170 to the human operator, countering the implication that the LLM possesses indepen-
171 dent agency or intention. By emphasising the tool-like nature of LLMs – implicitly
172 requiring a technique and purpose to be supplied by a human operator – this analogy
173 encourages users to approach these systems with a more critical and intentional mind-
174 set , potentially mitigating some of the risks associated with uncritical acceptance of
175 LLM outputs.
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182 ²What else can you call an interface that combines the utter lack of affordances of the command line with
183 something that never returns an error, nor provides guidance on its own effective use. People are forced into
184 self-reflection to improve their use of this interface, a failing that no other computer user interface has.

2.1 Difficulty	185
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Willison (2023) goes further when he explains:	187
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Using language models effectively is deceptively difficult.	189
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So many of the challenges involving language models come down to this: they look much,	191
much easier to use than they actually are.	192
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To get the most value out of them – and to avoid the many traps that they set for the	194
unwary user – you need to spend time with them, and work to build an accurate mental	195
model of how they work, what they are capable of and where they are most likely to go	196
wrong.	197
	198
I hope this “calculator for words” framing can help.	199
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We agree that ‘a calculator for words’ creates the idea of difficulty in a user’s head	202
– immediately, the user is reminded of struggling to set up an equation in maths class	203
and other intimidating scholastic tasks. Here is the aspect in which it most succeeds.	204
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We argue that the most salient aspects of this analogy are threefold:	206
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1. it underscores the necessity for user skill;	208
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2. it frames these systems as tools rather than databases powering search	210
engines; and	211
	212
3. it emphasises the need for users to articulate explicit intentions.	213
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These three criteria serve as essential benchmarks against which any alternative	216
analogy must be evaluated.	217
	218
A calculator implies a necessary floor for skill in a way that our conception of	219
a search engine or other human to whom we are conversing does not. While search	220
engines offer a seemingly straightforward interface – a search box that yields links and	221
information – calculators, especially more advanced models, require a more in-depth	222
understanding for optimal utilisation. This parallel extends to LLMs: just as graphing	223
and reverse Polish notation calculators demand thoughtful engagement, so too do the	224
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231 prompts submitted to large language models require nuance and skill reminiscent of
232 early search engine use.

234 The second salient aspect is the framing of these systems as tools. Drawing on Ihde
235 and Heideggerian philosophy, we can understand technology as a combination of tool
236 and technique employed to achieve a specific goal (Ihde, 1979). Conceptualising an
237 LLM’s interface as a tool, rather than a service, partner, or person, necessitates that
238 the user provide both technique and objective. This stands in contrast to personified
239 agents³ or search engines that appear to exercise independent agency in delivering
240 results.

241 The third aspect, intention, highlights the LLM’s lack of inherent intentional
242 agency by considering the difference between linking to intentionally created pages
243 versus the useful confabulation-of-tokens which is the LLMs primary action. While
244 we might perceive search engines, like Reddit, Wikipedia, and the rest of the internet,
245 as exercising discretion in mediating between facts and user queries, this discretion in
246 LLMs operates at the human programmer defined generative AI service layer rather
247 than within the LLM’s inference itself.

248 **Argument 2.1** (Modus ponens).

249 *P1. If an AI system lacks inherent intentional agency in its core operation (token
250 inference) and its outputs are primarily bounded by human-defined service layers,
251 then it is fundamentally different from search engines that link to intentionally
252 created content.*

253 *P2. LLMs lack inherent intentional agency in their core operation (token inference),
254 and their outputs are primarily determined by human-defined service layers (system
255 prompts and post-hoc interactions applied to token inference).*

256 *C. Therefore, LLMs are fundamentally different from search engines that link to
257 intentionally created content.*

258 ³To quote Douglas Adams: ‘The marketing division of the Sirius Cybernetics Corporation defines a robot
259 as “Your Plastic Pal Who’s Fun to Be With.”’ (Adams, 1995). It is noteworthy how some corporations
260 developing generative AI services seem to have adopted this as a design principle for their synthetic personae.

Generative AI services choose their system prompt, they choose what *post hoc* interactions to apply upon the token inference of the LLM. Thus, the output of the service is far more sensitive to user intention than the equivalent approach from a search engine. Thus, this is a worthwhile feature of the analogy, moving people away from thinking of these things as databases of facts which are curiously competent at communication.

This final point merits further exploration. The distinction between the LLM’s raw output and the service layer’s role in shaping the final response is crucial for understanding the system’s limitations and capabilities. Future research could delve deeper into how this layered approach influences user interaction and the potential for misinterpretation of LLM outputs.

2.2 Mitigating dissatisfaction

We teach that this analogy is an injunction for users to set up their context window – the full set of tokens used by an LLM to generate the inference of the next token – with the same thoughtfulness as they would use when entering inputs into a calculator. Users treating an LLM as a manipulator of known inputs leading to expected outputs will be disappointed less often with the outcome than those who treat it as a knowledge base, a search engine, or a friend. Reducing the infinite possibilities of the generative AI’s prompt box to ‘think of this as a calculator for words’ focuses the users’ minds quite effectively away from sad-making⁴ routes.

However, while this analogy serves as an effective cautionary device, steering audiences away from certain modes of interaction, it falls short in providing constructive guidance. As a primarily negative analogy, it is an incomplete conceptual tool for pedagogical purposes or comprehensive communication about LLMs. There is a pressing need for an analogy that elucidates and communicates the affordances of these services,

⁴We use the term ‘sad’ to refer to undesirable or unfortunate outputs mostly because characterising the full set of outputs which could lead to the operator’s sadness would take a paper in itself. Describing the outcome to be avoided is more efficient rather than the routes to that outcome.

323 the ways in which they can be used effectively, and the ways in which they can be
324 used to augment human capabilities.
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326 Furthermore, as [Hicks et al \(2024\)](#) succinctly assert in their provocative title 'Chat-
327 GPT is Bullshit,' these systems generate text without adherence to an underlying
328 reality. This fundamental characteristic renders them antithetical to the numerical
329 precision and contestability inherent in calculators. The stark contrast between the
330 deterministic nature of calculators and the probabilistic, reality-agnostic output of
331 LLMs further underscores the limitations of the 'calculator for words' analogy.
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337 **3 Contra Calculators for Words**

338 For all the non-anthropomorphic utility of this analogy, there exist many issues. First,
339 calculators are already involved in this conversation. In [Bonger and van der Wal \(2023\)](#)
340 in January 2023, they discuss how the current concern around these tools echoes the
341 concerns of calculators in classrooms from prior technological waves. [Bucci \(2023\)](#)
342 argues that the analogy provides deeply incorrect intuitions about the reliability of
343 calculators.
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350 Bucci says:

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352 'To put it differently, a calculator has a well-defined, well-scoped set of use cases, a well-
353 defined, well-scoped user interface, and a set of well-understood and expected behaviors
354 that occur in response to manipulations of that interface. ... Large language models, when
355 used to drive chatbots or similar interactive text-generation systems, have none of those
356 qualities. They have an open-ended set of unspecified use cases.' ([Bucci, 2023](#))
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360 Following Bucci's analysis, we can identify three principal flaws in the 'calculator
361 for words' analogy:
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- 364 1. It incorrectly suggests that LLMs and their associated services are deterministic,
365 unopinionated tools with clearly defined affordances.
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2. It implies that LLM outputs are reliable, contestable, and directly related to inputs	369
in a manner akin to calculators.	370
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3. It presupposes that we have a clear understanding of the appropriate uses for these	372
tools and can form unambiguous intentions and intuitions about their application.	373
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While Willison acknowledges the imprecision of his analogy, stating, ‘All analogies	376
are imperfect, but some are more imperfect than others’ (Willison, 2023), it is cru-	377
cial to examine these critiques in greater depth. Although we maintain that these	378
imperfections do not entirely invalidate the analogy, we argue that they constrain its	379
utility primarily to that of a negative, cautionary device. The analogy serves better	380
as a warning against certain misconceptions rather than as a guide for productive	381
engagement with LLMs.	382
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3.1 Determinism and affordances	389
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The primary critique of the ‘calculator for words’ analogy, as Willison himself acknowl-	391
edges, lies in the deterministic nature of calculators. When a calculator produces an	392
erroneous result, the error can almost invariably be traced back to incorrect user	393
input. There exists a clear, deterministic computational link between input patterns	394
and output patterns in calculators. A diligent investigator can reproduce the error by	395
verifying inputs against machine outputs, and through careful analysis, identify and	396
comprehend the specific bug that caused the computational fault.	397
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Furthermore, the affordances of calculators, even sophisticated ones like the TI-	400
83, are inherently constrained. They offer a finite set of operations, and each input	401
is either valid or invalid for these predetermined functions. This constrained nature	402
stands in stark contrast to the open-ended capabilities of LLMs.	403
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In our eyes, the most fundamental critique is this:	409
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Theorem 3.1. <i>A calculator, upon receiving invalid input, will give the user an error.</i>	411
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<i>A LLM, upon receiving invalid input, will give the user a valid response.</i>	413
	414

415 We assert that the differences between the constrained and well-known affordances
416 of a calculator and the utterly unconstrained input capabilities and always-responsive
417 output fundamentally breaks the utility of this analogy. Adding salt to the wound,
418 users should never use a LLM *qua* calculator, lest they be sad. While the analogy of
419 LLM prompts accepting word inputs akin to calculators accepting numerical inputs
420 has some merit – particularly in cautioning novice users against treating LLM-powered
421 services as authoritative search engines or sources of unvetted ‘slop’⁵—it falters under
422 closer scrutiny, as Bucci notes. The fundamental differences in determinism, error
423 handling, and output reliability between calculators and LLMs render the analogy
424 problematic for anything beyond a superficial comparison.
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433 **3.2 ChatGPT is Bullshit**

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435 As a nod towards [Hicks et al \(2024\)](#), a crucial issue with LLMs is that their output
436 – a stream of tokens with the highest statistical likelihood that appears to us as
437 coherent thought – is fundamentally disconnected from reality. This output, which can
438 be characterised as ‘bullshit’ in the philosophical sense⁶, is generated without regard
439 for an underlying truth or factual basis.
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443 LLMs infer signs without reference to their referents, producing the most statisti-
444 cally likely token sequence rather than the most accurate, faithful, or useful output.
445 This methodology stands in stark contrast to that of a calculator. Calculators operate
446 within well-defined numerical domains, executing computations based on established
447 mathematical principles. When a user inputs a number into a calculator, that number
448 corresponds to some aspect of reality – whether it represents a concrete quantity like
449 bottle caps or an abstract concept in trigonometry. This establishes a fundamental
450 link between the calculator’s operations and real-world phenomena. Furthermore, a
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⁵Slop, a term promoted by Willison, refers to: ‘But I’m increasingly of the opinion that sharing unreviewed content that has been artificially generated with other people is rude. Slop is the ideal name for this anti-pattern.’ ([Willison, 2024](#))

⁶Referring to the concept of ‘bullshit’ as developed in philosophical discourse, particularly by [Frankfurt \(2009\)](#)

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user can verify or replicate any step of a calculator’s process manually, underscoring the transparency and reliability of its operations.

We could assert that the scope of action within an LLM is infinitely greater than that of a non-programmable calculator⁷. We use the term infinitely here reservedly, as the only fundamental constraint is that of the context window: so long as the set of instructions and the answer fits within the context window, the LLM will gamely align to the *vibe* of the instructions and produce an answer – an answer without relation to reality.

Again, as Willison notes, all analogies are deficient. If they were full descriptions of the thing in itself, they wouldn’t be analogies. However, as this analogy is intended to dissuade from one specific sort of user interaction, we must see if in the intuitive consequences of its use, the harms outweigh the benefits. Even within a limited lies-to-novices sense, are there more appropriate warnings that we may give?

3.3 Appropriateness of use

When I speak in front of groups and ask them to raise their hands if they used the free version of ChatGPT, almost every hand goes up. When I ask the same group how many use GPT-4, almost no one raises their hand. I increasingly think the decision of OpenAI to make the “bad” AI free is causing people to miss why AI seems like such a huge deal to a minority of people that use advanced systems and elicits a shrug from everyone else. (Mollick, 2023b)

At the end of the day, we know what purposes a calculator is appropriate *for*: it is a tool which performs mathematical calculations. We know when to reach for one. Those who use them often and who have a good sense for numbers know when the answer is inconsistent with reality before having to manually double-check. We have also had

⁷This is to exclude the inevitable case where an LLM can be instantiated within a general computer presenting as a calculator

507 calculators and their predecessors (the slide rule, the abacus, and precomputed lookup
508 tables, amongst other specialised tools) for millennia ([Adkins, 1956](#), 131).

510 We have been in the GPT-4 era, at the time of writing, for only slightly over a
511 year⁸. For those who are paying attention, as per Mollick above, we are busy applying
512 generative AI to every task, and getting a simulacrum of useful output on some of
513 them. Few people share the same conceptions of the appropriate and the possible
514 extents of LLM operation, not to mention that with every new iteration from OpenAI
515 or Anthropic we have to start again when assessing appropriate and possible modes
516 of operation.
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522 It is this sheer novelty and pace of innovation that advises caution here. While we
523 seek to describe, by analogy, parts or aspects of generative AI serving forth an LLM’s
524 token inference – the very capabilities of the things we are describing are changing
525 under our feet. For instance, Anthropic’s Claude 3.5 Sonnet, released shortly before
526 this paper’s composition, demonstrates markedly improved mathematical proficiency
527 compared to its predecessors. Yet, its 96.4% accuracy rate for grade-school math-
528 ematics still falls short of the standard required for a reliable computational tool
529 ([Anthropic, 2024b](#)).

530 Does the analogy of a calculator-for-words prove sufficiently robust to guide our
531 thinking in this time of great change in LLM capabilities? Partially – it does still serve
532 as a useful precautionary analogy against treating it more like a search engine, or a
533 plastic pal who is nice to be with. But this critique is more useful insofar as we need
534 to consider, in our proposed new analogy, something that is robust to this rapid pace
535 of change.
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546 ⁸The authors hold that this current era began with the release of Bing Sydney on 4 Feb, 2023, rather
547 than GPT-3.5 in November 2022. We would never have to write this paper about GPT-3.5 class models.

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4 Discussion	553
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Before we consider what may be a more apt analogy, it is worth considering the pros	555
and cons of the use of ‘a calculator for words.’ We believe, on the whole, that this	556
analogy is useful. It is limited, mostly useful in the negative sense, but very persuasive	557
to audiences who think of it as a search engine or friend. The analogy is simple and	558
serves to draw back the curtains somewhat on the nature of these LLMs and the	559
generative AI services which provide access to them.	560
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In this section, we will consider the above through three lenses:	565
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1. what intuitions are sparked by the deployment of this analogy in its listeners;	567
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2. how useful is it as a pedagogical tool to presenters; and	569
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3. do we think that people exposed to the analogy comprehend it and its limitations?	571
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4.1 Intuitions of the analogy	574
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The idea falls apart on deeper inspection. It does not reward consideration, nor does	576
the idea of a calculator share useful ontological or epistemological similarities with	577
any LLM published to date.	578
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Here, it is less useful.	581
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4.2 Pedagogical utility of the analogy	584
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From our experience teaching about the pragmatic use and philosophical implications	586
of Generative AI, most audiences react usefully when exposed to this concept. How-	587
ever, our treatment of the topic is light. It is useful as part of a <i>larger</i> presentation,	588
but less salient in deeper dives.	589
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We use this concept as a way to teach people to pay attention to the context	593
window, setting up the context window, and expecting specific token inference from	594
that resulting setup. The analogy adjusts the audiences’ epistemic orientation to the	595
interfaces provided by these services.	596
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599 Here, it is useful.

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602 **4.3 Comprehensibility of the analogy**

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604 From our audiences, and from the feedback Willison has received, it is clear that

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606 listeners anchor on different salient aspects of the idea-of-calculator: its reliability,

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608 its use as a tool, and its comprehensibility are all items that Willison and Bucci

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610 have touched upon. The fact that disclaimers and a specific reading-in to the facet

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612 which is useful is necessary for effective communication diminishes the utility of this

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614 analogy. Despite that, when that detail is employed, there does seem to be mutual

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616 Here, it is mostly useful.

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619 **5 Large Language Models: Maps of no Territory**

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621 LLMs, as demonstrated previously, are often misunderstood. To elucidate their nature

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623 and potential, we propose a new, more suited, analogy: LLMs are like maps of no

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625 territory.

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627 This section aims to explore and substantiate this analogy, demonstrating how

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629 LLMs, much like maps, offer symbols without referent like a map offering a naviga-

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631 tional aid devoid of a fixed, underlying reality. By examining the concepts of maps,

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633 territories, and the skills required to navigate this novel terrain, we can better under-

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635 stand how to utilise these AI tools effectively. We will be borrowing from two of Borges

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637 works: the infinite library of *The Library of Babel* and the map-territory distinction

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639 from *On Exactitude in Science*

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641 **5.1 Maps, Territories, and Borges' analogies**

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643 ...In that Empire, the Art of Cartography attained such Perfection that the map of a single

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645 Province occupied the entirety of a City, and the map of the Empire, the entirety of a

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Province. In time, those Unconscionable Maps no longer satisfied, and the Cartographers
 Guilds struck a Map of the Empire whose size was that of the Empire, and which coincided
 point for point with it. ... (Borges and Hurley, 1998)

Maps are representations of a territory, abstracting and simplifying its features to
 aid in navigation. A map is a tool that illustrates the spatial relationships between
 different locations, allowing us to navigate and understand physical spaces. Maps
 serve as guides, offering a usefully simplified version of reality that helps us reach
 our destinations, comprehend the layout of an area, and make informed decisions
 about where to go and how to get there. A territory is the actual physical space or
 reality that a map aims to represent. It encompasses the real-world environments and
 locations that exist independently of any representation. Territories are concrete, filled
 with tangible objects, geographical features, and landmarks. While maps provide an
 abstract, simplified depiction of territories, the territories themselves are the complex,
 multifaceted realities that we interact with directly.

A ‘map of no territory’ is akin to Wittgenstein’s notion of nonsensical sentences,
 in that both are systems of representation that fail to correspond to any real structure
 or state of affairs. Just as a nonsensical sentence lacks a logical form that mirrors
 reality, a map without a corresponding territory lacks a spatial form that mirrors any
 physical location. Both highlight the critical role of correspondence in rendering a
 representation meaningful and useful. (TLP, 3.24)

However, this is not to say that maps are in a hyper-real scenario: the normal out-
 puts of a cartographer’s work do maintain a faithful representation of the real at a
 1:X abstraction. A calculator maintains a referential link to the bottle caps or algo-
 rithms that it is manipulating at a 1:1 abstraction. An LLM, however, is useful for
 when it accidentally produces signs which, we as the reader, find to have useful ref-
 erents. In the palimpsest of statistical abstractions that is the no-map set of weights
 produced by model training, it is by accident that the human entered signs – with the

691 human’s referents – are converted to potentially useful output. Here, we must remem-
692 ber the term ‘slop:’ Slop, is *unreviewed* LLM output. It is the act of reviewing and
693 editorial decisions which re-referentialises the LLM’s sign-production. Thus, when
694 the LLM produces output, the nonsense it produces is only useful *by accident*. Hap-
695 pily, the accident of utility occurs frequently enough to then make this tool worthy of
696 our attention.

701 Borges’ analogy of the map-territory distinction vividly captures the evolution of
702 precision in cartography: as the Art of Cartography advanced, maps grew increas-
703 ingly detailed and precise. In his exaggerated narrative, maps eventually became so
704 vast and accurate that they spanned the very territories they depicted. According to
705 Borges, cartographers reached a level of perfection where a map of a province could
706 fill an entire city, and an empire’s map could cover an entire province. His hyperbolic
707 portrayal highlights the ambition and intricacy of cartographers.

712 In Borges’s analogy around the exactitude of science, maps (science) attained such
713 scale and precision that they no longer merely represented territories – they effectively
714 became them. This evolution parallels the role of search engines in today’s digital
715 age. In this analogical framework, a search engine serves as a tool for exploring a vast
716 digital domain, indexing and retrieving information from a purely digital territory of
717 works and data. And, in the same wise, the search engine has become the web in 2024.

722 LLMs operate similarly to maps, but – we argue – without a tangible terri-
723 tory. They generate language based on abstract representations of statistical patterns
724 within their source texts, devoid of direct access to real-world referents. This abstrac-
725 tion means that LLMs offer interpretations and manipulations of language divorced
726 from physical contexts or real-world referential anchors. Therefore, in the context of
727 digital spaces and language generation, LLMs can be understood as maps of no terri-
728 tory – tools that can navigate and manipulate linguistic landscapes without grounding
729 in a specific physical reality or with direct referentiality to a specific text.

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5.2 Borges’ analogies and LLMs	737
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Argument 5.1 (Modus ponens).	739
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<i>P1. If LLMs generate language based on abstract representations without direct access</i>	741
<i>to real-world referents, then LLMs are like maps of no territory.</i>	742
	743
<i>P2. LLMs generate language based on abstract representations without direct access to</i>	744
<i>real-world referents.</i>	745
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<i>C. Therefore, LLMs are like maps of no territory.</i>	747
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	749
LLMs, as our proposed map-analogues, generate language based on statistical	750
relationships learned from vast amounts of text, creating abstract representations of	751
language patterns and structures. LLMs do not have direct access to or understanding	752
of the real-world referents of the language they generate. Their outputs are based	753
solely on the statistical correlations within the data they were trained on, an analogue	754
of no territory. Therefore, LLMs function as maps of no territory – they provide	755
navigational aids (language outputs) that are abstract and internally consistent but	756
not directly grounded in a specific real-world reality.	757
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5.3 How is it like, then, interacting with LLMs?	765
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Interacting effectively with LLMs is akin to assuming the role of a librarian of Babel	767
in Borges’ Infinite Library. The Infinite Library symbolises an infinite repository con-	768
taining every book ever written and all conceivable books. Within this analogical	769
framework, the outputs generated by LLMs can be likened to books housed within	770
this infinite library, demanding adept navigation to extract meaningful content.	771
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Much like the librarian in Borges’ tale, an adept user of an LLM possesses the skill	775
to navigate through countless texts and identify those that are pertinent. This skill	776
goes beyond mere familiarity with the content; it involves the ability to discern factual	777
accuracy without in-text reliability signifiers, explore the possible worlds depicted	778
in the texts, and strategically utilise the information gleaned. The librarian – and	779
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783 by extension, the skilled LLM user – therefore, not only comprehends the breadth
784 of available knowledge but also excels in selecting and interpreting texts amidst an
785 overwhelming expanse of information. This analogy underscores the complexity and
786 nuance involved in interacting with LLMs, where users must navigate through vast
787 datasets and statistical associations to derive meaningful insights and outputs.
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5.4 Use LLMs effectively: Skilful Navigation to Find Meaningful Content

Navigating an LLM involves interpreting and applying these abstract representations – the statistical relationships or "traces" – without a corresponding real-world reference. Navigating a map of no territory, such as an LLM, requires understanding and manipulating abstract representations rather than physical spaces or tangible referents. In the case of an LLM, navigation involves interpreting and applying these abstract representations – which we term 'traces' within the model's statistical relationships. Unlike traditional maps that we use as a guide through physical landscapes with clear landmarks and spatial relationships, LLMs operate within a digital realm where language and information are the primary currencies. These traces enable a user, through careful review, to transform potentially 'nonsensical sentences' into useful output, as a thoughtful user can identify useful traces and use them to re-referentialise the tokens produced by an LLM.

To navigate an LLM effectively, users must comprehend the nuances of these abstract traces embedded within the model's data. These traces are not tied to specific physical objects or locations, but instead reflect the latent statistical patterns 'learned' from vast amounts of text data. User interaction with these traces occurs through the input of prompts or queries, with an expectation – often naive – that the model will generate coherent and contextually appropriate responses based on

its learned associations. There is also the long-learned expectation that somewhere, anywhere, there exists a site claiming such things.

Navigating an LLM involves, notably, a different kind of mapping interpretation and use that is conditioned on the first realisation that LLMs manipulate language patterns rather than a spatial navigation through physical terrain. Users must adjust their expectations from navigating concrete maps to interpreting and utilising the statistical mappings within the model, aiming for useful and coherent outputs rather than direct representations of physical reality.

The effective use of LLMs, therefore, requires skilful navigation of the infinite library to find meaningful content. It depends upon gaining or developing the proficiency in manoeuvring through these three interconnected levels of mapping, which can be seen as analogous to a teacher’s mental maps ([Word et al, 2021](#), Building Skill with Practice):

- **Expertise Map:** This level represents the user’s foundational understanding of a topic – their existing knowledge, beliefs, and perceptions. It forms the basis from which users initiate interactions with the LLM, providing context and guiding their approach to querying the model.
- **Incomplete but Sufficient Map:** Users develop this framework to engage effectively with the LLM, similar to how teachers methodologically communicate a high-level map to foster understanding in students. This map is incomplete but sufficient, focusing on establishing meaningful connections between key concepts and nuances. Through feedback mechanisms, users refine their approach, shaping interactions with the LLM to maximise utility and coherence of outputs. Strategies, techniques, and linguistic patterns are employed to craft prompts that convey concepts and relationships, enhancing the relevance of responses aligned with informational needs.

875 • **The Map of a Map of no Territory:** Within the LLM itself, this level
876 represents abstract representations – statistical mappings and learned
877 associations derived from vast textual datasets⁹. Unlike physical maps,
878 this digital map operates in a domain of language patterns and textual
879 correlations. Inputs trigger the model to synthesise responses based on
880 learned patterns. Users navigate this map by interpreting and lever-
881 aging statistical associations effectively, understanding that outputs
882 reflect the model’s training data rather than direct representations of
883 physical reality. Analogous to a teacher iterating on their students’ men-
884 tal maps through various feedback mechanisms, users engage in refining
885 their approach to the LLM. They strive to create useful correspon-
886 dences and refine ineffective ones, ultimately shaping their interaction
887 with the model to enhance the relevance and coherence of its outputs.
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898 **5.5 What are the requirements to successfully navigate a map** 899 **of no territory?** 900

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902 The effectiveness of using LLMs requires proficiency in manoeuvring through these
903 three interconnected levels of mapping navigation. Users must align their own world-
904 view and symbolic understanding with the techniques needed to interact with the
905 model’s abstract representations effectively. By doing so, they can harness the poten-
906 tial of LLMs to generate insightful and contextually relevant outputs tailored to their
907 informational and worldly objectives.
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911 We say that an analogy more apt than ‘a calculator for words’ is ‘a map with
912 no territory.’ LLMs manipulate tokens – signs divorced from referents – and present
913 infinite maps of traces from many territories. A successful user navigates these maps
914 by developing effective mental models of the tool, enhancing their techniques, and
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919 ⁹See [Anthropic \(2024a\)](#)’s exploration with making model fixated on the Golden Gate Bridge. They were
920 able to navigate their model’s map and, as it were, draw upon its paper.

aligning objectives more realistically. Much like a teacher fosters understanding in students, users establish per-model frameworks to engage effectively with LLMs, focusing on meaningful connections and leveraging old prompts – well-worn trails through the library – for coherent outputs.

Those who solely focus on the tools or expect generative AI services to autonomously handle map conversions miss the map due to the absence of a direct territory. Understanding and navigating these digital maps requires interpreting and utilising the underlying models’ statistical associations effectively, acknowledging that LLM outputs reflect learned patterns rather than direct representations of physical reality. Thus, interacting with an LLM involves navigating these nuanced maps of the digital landscape, aiming not for literal translations but for insightful and contextually relevant outputs aligned with informational, worldly needs.

6 Conclusion

An effective use of an LLM requires a skilful navigation to find meaningful content. It demands proficiency in navigating three interconnected levels of mapping. Users must align their own worldview and linguistic understanding with the techniques necessary to interact with the model’s abstract representations. This alignment enables users to harness LLMs’ potential for generating insightful, contextually relevant outputs tailored to their worldly practice.

We compare LLMs to “maps of no territory,” where they manipulate tokens without direct referents and generate expansive maps of traces from various sources. Effective users navigate these maps by

1. skilfully interpreting the traces provided by the interaction with the LLM,
2. developing a framework to engage effectively with the LLM, and
3. navigate this map by interpreting and leveraging statistical associations effectively.

967 Thus, the effective user demonstrates an understanding that outputs reflect the
968 model’s training data rather than direct representations of physical reality.

969 Dismissing these three conditions, and expecting AI services to handle map con-
970 versions, overlooks the essence of navigating these digital maps. Understanding and
971 navigating these maps requires interpreting and utilising statistical associations effec-
972 tively, recognising that LLM outputs reflect ‘learned’ patterns rather than direct
973 representations of physical reality. Therefore, interacting with an LLM involves nav-
974 igating these nuanced digital landscapes, aiming not for literal translations but for
975 mastering a skilful navigation to find meaningful content.
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982 983 **7 Acknowledgements** 984

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991 992 **References** 993

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